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Amperometric Determination of Manganese(II) with 2-Hydroxy-1-Acetonaphthoneoxime*

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THERE is a paucity of literature on the amperometric determination of manganese(II), particularly using oximes as titrants. During a detailed investigation on the utility of 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime (2-HANO) and its isomer, 1-hydroxy-2-acetonaphthoneoxime (1-HANO)¹ as analytical reagents, it was observed that both the reagents give dark green precipitates with Mn(II) at pH 8.0-8.5. These reactions were utilised for the amperometric determination of Mn(II) in view of the favourable polarographic behaviour of Mn(II). The results of investigations on the use of 2-HANO as an amperometric titrant for Mn(II) are presented here. The reagent has already been used for gravimetric^{2,3} and amperometric⁴ determination of copper, nickel and palladium.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime was prepared⁵, recrystallised from rectified spirit and vacuum dried. A standard solution (0.025 M) was prepared in rectified spirit. A stock solution of manganese sulphate was also prepared and standardised⁶. The apparatus used for the amperometric titration was the same as described earlier⁶.

The polarographic behaviour of Mn(II) was studied at d.m.e. in presence of NH₄Cl-NH₄OH buffer of pH 8.0-8.5. The reagent did not give a reduction wave in ammoniacal medium. Hence the amperometric determination of Mn(II) was carried out at an applied potential of -1.7 V (vs SCE).

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Procedure :

To the aliquots of standard manganese sulphate solution (0.99-9.52 mg Mn) were added 20 ml ammonium chloride (1 M), 5 ml ammonium hydroxide (1 M), 2 ml Triton —X— 100 solution and 5 ml rectified spirit and the total volume made up to 80 ml with distilled water. The solution was deaerated by passing a stream of pure hydrogen for 15 min and then titrated with a standard solution of the reagent running down from a 5-ml microburette. The current readings were noted at an applied potential of -1.7 V (vs SCE) after each addition of the reagent followed by deaeration. A plot of current readings corrected for volume changes against the volume of titrant gave an L-shaped curve. Manganese (0.99-9.52 mg) could thus be determined with an average error of $\pm 0.43\%$. Six determinations of 1.972 mg manganese gave a standard deviation of 0.0006 mg and a relative mean error of $\pm 0.05\%$.

In the case of lower amounts of manganese, higher values were obtained as the concentration of ammonia and alcohol were increased, which might have been due to the solubility of the manganese complex formed.

Studies of Interferences :

Copper, palladium and zinc did not interfere, as they did not give any precipitate under the experimental conditions. The interferences due to iron(III) and aluminium(III) could be prevented by the addition of sodium fluoride solution (0.5 M). Cobalt(II) was masked by ammonium thiocyanate solution (0.5 M). Masking nickel by cyanide was of no use. Hence, a prior separation of nickel from manganese was considered essential.

Determination of copper and manganese from the same solution :

The reactivity of the reagent with two metals under different experimental conditions such as applied potential and pH of quantitative precipitation facilitates their determination from binary mixtures without separation. This principle was used for the determination of copper and nickel from the same solution by many workers^{4,6-8}. The same was extended for the determination of copper and manganese from the same solution. Aliquots of standard solutions of copper sulphate and manganese sulphate were taken in the wider limb of the H-cell. A dilute solution of sodium hydroxide (1 M) was added dropwise until a slight but permanent precipitate of the hydroxides of the metals was obtained. The precipitate was just dissolved by the addition of HCl (1 M). To this were added 25 ml ammonium chloride solution (1 M), 2 ml Triton —X— 100 solution and 5 ml rectified spirit and the total volume made up to 80 ml. Addition of ammonium chloride was preferred to an acetate buffer (pH 4.0-4.5) to avoid addition of large amounts of ammonia required to raise the pH in the subsequent determination of manganese. Copper was determined at an applied potential of -0.4 V (vs SCE).

The titration was continued till the galvanometer reading showed no further decrease on the addition of the reagent. At this stage, the titration was stopped temporarily and the applied potential changed to -1.7 V (vs SCE). The pH was adjusted to 8.0-8.5 and manganese determined following the procedure developed. Typical results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF COPPER AND MANGANESE WITH 2-HANO

Copper (mg)			Manganese (mg)		
Taken	Found	Error %	Taken	Found	Error %
3.006	3.018	+0.88	0.986	0.990	+0.41
2.004	2.013	+0.40	1.972	1.980	+0.41
1.002	1.012	+0.80	2.958	2.966	+0.27

The present study thus shows that manganese can be conveniently determined with 2-HANO as titrant. The results are comparable to those obtained with 1-HANO¹. Literature records no procedure for the simultaneous determination of copper(II) and manganese(II).

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Platinum(II) Heterochelates Derived from Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid and Bidentate NN-Donor Ligands

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ALTHOUGH ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) has been used extensively as a coordinating ligand towards various metal ions¹, very

little has appeared on the platinum(II) complexes of this ligand^{2,3}. Since the report² of the synthesis of *cis*-dichloro(ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid)platinum(II) in 1956, no work has appeared on the reactivity of this compound towards bidentate ligands. We thought it worthwhile to test the reactivity of the complex and in this note we report the use of the complex as the starting material for the synthesis of platinum(II) heterochelates of the type [Pt(EDTA)(BB)]Cl₂ where BB = ethylenediamine, trimethylenediamine, propylenediamine, 3-aminopyridine, *orthophenanthroline* or 2,2'-bipyridyl.

Experimental

Disodium ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid was purchased from SD's Lab. Chem. Industry. Potassium tetrachloroplatinate(II) and dichloro(ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid)platinum(II) were synthesized by published procedures^{2,4}. Ethylenediamine was a product of Sarabhai M. Chemicals Co. Trimethylenediamine was obtained from Fluka AG (Switzerland). Propylenediamine, 3-aminopyridine, 2,2'-bipyridyl and *orthophenanthroline* were purchased from Aldrich Chemical Co. (U.S.A.).

Analyses and physical measurements of the complexes were carried out as described previously⁵.

General method of synthesis of the complexes :

An aqueous solution of dichloro(ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid)platinum(II) (0.56 g; 1 mmole in 10 ml) was added to an aqueous solution of aliphatic diamine (1 mmole in 15 ml) or an ethanolic solution of aromatic amine (1 mmole in 5 ml). The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 30 min with occasional stirring and then cooled in an ice-bath. The separated precipitate was suction filtered, washed with cold water followed by ethanol and dried under vacuum. In case of 2,2'-bipyridyl the compound separated during reflux. All the complexes except [Pt(EDTA)(bipy/phen)]Cl₂ were recrystallized from water. Yield ~60%. The analytical data are given in Table I.

Results and Discussion

The treatment of *cis*-dichloro(ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid)platinum(II) with bidentate ligands (BB) leads to the substitution of two *cis*-chloride ions by one molecule of BB and heterochelates of the type [Pt(EDTA)(BB)]Cl₂ are formed. The electrolytic conductance measurements in water indicate bi-univalent nature of the complexes ($\Lambda_M = 215-229 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)⁶. The complexes are diamagnetic indicating square planar structure of the complexes.

In the ir spectra of the complexes the strong band in the range 1690-1695 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the non-coordinated carboxyl carbonyl group of EDTA moiety⁷. The presence of this band in *cis*-dichloro(ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid)platinum(II) and in the heterochelates indicates that EDTA is behaving as a bidentate ligand and the four carboxylic acid